

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON SELECTED PSYCHOLOGICAL VARIABLES AMONG FOOTBALL PLAYERS

Dr. M. Madan Mohan

Associate Professor, Department of Physical Education, A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College,
Poondi, Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. M. Madan Mohan, “Effect of Yogic Practices on Selected Psychological Variables among Football Players”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 5, Issue 2, Page Number 11-13, 2020.

Copy Right: © IJSRME, 2020 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of yogic practices on selected psychological variables of football players. In this study, 30 players from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given any treatment. The yogic practices was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by paired ‘t’ test. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14. It was observed that the experimental group showed significant reduction in anxiety and stress than the control group.

Key Words: Yogic Practices, Anxiety, Stress.

Introduction:

Yogic of the past had not paid very much attention to the body, as they focused all their energy on contemplation and meditation. The new generation of yogis however, developed a system where different exercises in conjunction with deep breathing and meditation, would help keep a body young and prolong life. Yoga is like a blessing for those who love to have fit body. It is extremely beneficial in strength and endurance building. Sages and saints from centuries in India have performed this miraculous art to achieve a stress free temper and disease free body. Yoga through its different asana helps in developing a better coordination between different body organs along with your mind and your soul leaving you feel extremely fit and fine. Apart from providing you with vigor and activeness, yoga is also helpful in healing the diseases persisting in your body thus leaving you with more strength and endurance. In recent times there is a growing awareness among the people about the efficacy and utility of yoga in keeping one fit at physical, mental, emotional, social and spiritual planes. These systems are emerging as the effective methods and means to improve the total personality and to build a healthy society. Above all these systems are adopted as a way of life rather than a mode of treatment (Andre, 1987).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of yogic practices on selected psychological variables of football players. In this study, 30 players from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given any treatment. The yogic practices was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by paired ‘t’ test. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14.

Results:

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Pre and Post Test Means of Experimental and Control Group on Selected Physical Fitness Variables

S.No	Variables	Pre Test Mean	Post Test Mean
1	Anxiety	Exp:20.23	Exp:17.98
		Con:21.76	Con:20.55
2	Stress	Exp: 45.47	Exp:38.33
		Con: 44.33	Con:43.98

Table 2: Computation of ‘t’ Ratio Between the Pre Test and Post Test Means of Anxiety of Experimental and Control Group

S.No	Variables	Mean diff	SD	σ DM	‘t’ ratio
1	Anxiety	Exp: 2.25	Exp: 0.36	Exp: 0.13	8.24*
		Con: 1.21	Con: 0.30	Con: 0.09	1.77

* Significant at 0.05 level

An examination of table II indicates that the obtained ‘t’ ratio for anxiety of experimental group was 8.24. The obtained ‘t’ ratio on anxiety was found to be greater than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be significant. The obtained ‘t’ ratio for anxiety of control group was 1.77. The obtained ‘t’ ratio on anxiety was found to be lesser than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be not significant. The mean scores of anxiety of experimental group and control group was shown graphically in figure 1.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Showing the Pre Mean and Post Mean of Anxiety of Experimental and Control Group

Table 3: Computation of ‘t’ Ratio Between the Pre Test and Post Test Means of Stress of Experimental and Control Group

S.No	Variables	Mean Diff	SD	σ DM	‘t’ ratio
1	Stress	Exp: 7.14	Exp: 0.71	Exp: 0.23	13.79*
		Con: 0.35	Con: 1.61	Con: 0.47	1.74

* Significant at 0.05 level

An examination of table III indicates that the obtained ‘t’ ratio for stress of experimental group was 13.79. The obtained ‘t’ ratio on stress was found to be greater than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be significant. The obtained ‘t’ ratios for stress of control group was 1.74. The obtained ‘t’ ratio on stress was found to be lesser than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be not significant. The mean scores of stress of experimental group and control group was shown graphically in figure 2.

Figure 2: Bar Diagram Showing the Pre Mean and Post Mean of Stress of Experimental and Control Group

Conclusion:

It was observed that the experimental group showed significant reduction in anxiety and stress than the control group.

References:

1. Andre Van Lysebeth, (1987). Yoga Self – Taught, Delhi: Tarage Paper Back.
2. Bera, T, K., Rajapurkar,M,V.(1993). Body composition, cardiovascular endurance and anaerobic power of yogic practitioner. Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology, Vol.37 (3): PP.225-8.
3. Bertisch,S,M., Wee,C,C., McCarthy,E,P (2008).Use of complementary and alternative therapies by overweight and obese adults. Journal of Research and Education in Complementary and Integrative Medical Therapies, Vol.16 (7): PP.1610-5.
4. Chatterjee,F., Bruce,S,A., Woldege,R,C. (2010)Effect of yogic Exercises on human Growth hormone in a middle aged group: a pilot study. Yoga Mimamsa a Quarterly Journal, vol XLII.1, PP.40-47.
5. Chen, K, M., and Tseng,W,S.(2008).Effect of newly developed silver yoga exercise program for female seniors. Journal of Nursing and Resarch, Vol.6 (1): PP.37-46.
6. Chen, T, L., Mao,H,C., Lai ,C,H., Li ,C,Y., Kuo,C,H.(2009). The effect of yoga exercise intervention on health related physical fitness in school-age asthmatic children. The Journal of Nursing-Taiwan, Vol.56 (2): PP.42-52.
7. Chidambararaja.S. (2014). Effect of Yogic Practices and Aerobic Exercises on Strength Endurance Self-Concept and Blood Pressure. International Journal of Recent Research and Applied Studies, 1, 6(7), 33 - 36.
8. Choquette,S., Riesco,E., Cormier,E., Dion,T., Aubertin,L,M., Dionne,I,J.(2010). Effects of soya is flavones and exercise on body composition and clinical risk factors of cardiovascular diseases in overweight postmenopausal women: a 6-month double-blind controlled trial. The British Journal of Nutrition, Vol.17: PP.1-11.
9. Moorthy A.M. & David Manual Raju, J. (1983). Yoga for Health. Madras: M.J.Publishers.
10. Morrow, James R. (2005). Measurement and Evaluation in Human Performance, (3ED), Champaign Illinois: Human Kinetics Publishers Inc.,